

Socio-economic Activities and COVID-19 Outbreak: Experience from Low-income Families in Enugu and Ebonyi States, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined socio-economic activities and COVID-19 outbreak amongst low-income families in Enugu and Ebonyi States, Nigeria. following the outbreak of COVID-19 and its spread, Nigeria queued into international health mitigation standard to enforce compulsory stay at home, social distancing, constant washing of hands, use of hand sanitizers, closure of schools and public places, and border closures to contain the spread of the virus. The study employed survey research design whereby 42 respondents were selected purposively from Enugu and Ebonyi States of Nigeria. Interviews were administered on the respondents. Findings show that COVID-19 pandemic had destructive effects on socio-economic wellbeing of low-income families in Nigeria, ranging from job loss, increase in poverty level, increase in food insecurity, increase in violence, high cost of living, and lack of adequate social security. This study recommends that the Nigerian government should be proactive in drafting and implementing effective social security that will recognize the rights of every Nigerian and also guarantee social benefits to people in time of tragedy. More so, investing in health, social, and economic infrastructures is germane.

Keywords: Socio-economic, COVID-19, Families, Low Income Families, lockdown

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted family routines, relationships, projects and sociability all over the world as well as threatened the health, income, social arrangement, and well-being of individual families (Gouveia, Ramos & Will, (2021). Due to the high rate of infectivity and spread of coronavirus to the different regions of the world, the World Health Organization declared a state of international public health emergency on 30 January 2020 and Covid-19 was declared a global pandemic on 11 March 2020 (Eze, Ajah, Nwonovo & Atama, 2021; Kutsar & Kurvet-Kaosaar, 2021). The pandemic had a huge socio-economic impact on Nigeria, which has one of the highest rates of multidimensional low income and poor families in the world (UNDP & NBS, 2021), and which according to UNDP (2020), ranked 161st out of 189th countries in human development index. The country was forced to take a giant step to contain the pandemic when the country first index case was recorded on 27th February 2020. The harsh social effect of the Coronavirus crisis was felt through the imposition of movement restrictions in the country, and some of the preventive measures that were imposed to control the spread of the virus include: restricting non-essential activities, schools and universities closures, encouraging people to stay home, the lockdown of entire cities, which required essential businesses to run skeletal operations and employees working from home (Ozili, 2020). These measures inevitably affected the economic situation of the country which unreservedly affected the well-being of individual families especially low income families. Individuals and their families were then forced to find ways of dealing with feelings of uncertainty, insecurity and anxiety while engaging in collective displays of solidarity and altruistic actions (Gouveia, Ramos & Will, 2021).

Nigeria was worst hit by the effect of COVID-19 and the consequent lockdown due to the fact that the economy which depended mostly on oil had already suffered a rapid decline in oil prices in international market (Olubusoye & Ogbonna, 2021). The security challenges arising from insurgent violence from Boko-Haram, banditry, unknown gunmen, kidnapping and so on, and the fallout from the pandemic pushed the Nigerian economy back into a recession; its deepest in over four decades with real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) contracting for two consecutive quarters by 6.1% and 3.6% in 2nd quarters and 3rd quarters of 2020, respectively (UNDP & NBS, 2021). The full outbreak of the coronavirus in 2020 changed the normal working of the Nigerian economy, it affected many lives and livelihoods, with many families and individuals especially the families of low-income earners struggling to adjust and cope with its bizarre effects (Olunfemi & Ojekunle, 2021).

Lockdown during COVID-19 caused hike in the cost of food prices and high rate of poverty on various families in Nigeria particularly low income earners. About 30 percent of households interviewed in June 2020 by National Bureau of Statistics, could not meet up to their essential needs due to lack of money or other resources (NBS, 2020), and there was no alternative means of earnings. In a National General Household Survey conducted by National Bureau of Statistics (2019), it was revealed that 32% of Nigerians experienced food shortages over the last 12 months proceeding the time of the survey while 44% of the households indicated not being able to eat nutritious and healthy food because they simply could not afford it. It was amidst this socio-economic situation that COVID-19 and its subsequent economic fallout occurred in Nigeria (National Economic Summit Group, 2021).

To mitigate the effect of the pandemic on low income families and businesses, the government and the private sectors embarked on a series of interventions (Eze, Ugwuoke & Igwe, 2022). The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) in collaboration with key private sector

players set up the “Private Sector Coalition Against COVID19” (CACOVID) to mobilize funds from the private sectors in order to support the government’s efforts to mitigate effects of the crisis whereby they were able to raise approximately the sum of N27 billion (Olubusoye & Ogbonna, 2021; United Nations Women Nigeria, 2020). The Federal Government of Nigeria on its part approved N500 billion for the upgrade of healthcare facilities in the country, so also the Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Disaster Management swung into action and distributed a sum of N20,000 to households that had been profiled and included in their database as representing the poorest of the poor (Opeyemi, 2020; Nigeria Economic Summit Group, 2021). Also, many state governments and individuals created food banks to cushion the socio-economic effect of the Covid-19 lockdown on vulnerable households.

Though, both the federal and state governments revealed that the monetary and food palliatives were for the most vulnerable in the society, but there were no laid down parameters for determining the most vulnerable. This is because in many states in the country, the so-called palliatives were hijacked by politicians (Eranga, 2020), then the most vulnerable families were left without help. In as much as the importance of interventions to provide relief for the vulnerable in a crisis cannot be overemphasized, it is equally important that the interventions delivered to the families are in line with the actual needs of the families (Olubusoye & Ogbonna, 2021). Many families in Nigeria were not aware of governments’ palliatives because there was no equity in the distribution to the masses. That was the reason why there were lamentations by people concerning the palliatives as was reported in a national newspaper, Business Day on April 19, 2020, that “It is lamentation and bitter wailing in Lagos and parts of the country as Nigerians complain that the stimulus packages announced by the Federal and Lagos State governments to cushion the effects of the lockdown imposed on some States and the Federal Capital Territory to contain the further spread of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic have not been sincerely deployed” It was believed that a segment of the society hijacked the palliatives for themselves and their families while the low income families were not attended to. Previous studies researched on the socio-economic effects of COVID-19 on families and economy in Nigeria (see: Balarabe, 2020; Okorundu et al, 2021; Abubakar et al, 2021) but specific focus on socio-economic situation of low income families due to COVID-19 was not examined with detailed empirical attention. This study therefore sets out to fill this gap by assessing the socio-economic effects of COVID-19 on low income families in Enugu and Ebonyi States. It will equally assess the government policies to mitigate the effects and then proffer some solutions to curb the problems.

Literature Review

Low Income Families:

According to Akani and Anyike (2020), low-income earners primarily comprised of lower-level citizens, lower level office workers or unskilled workers who are typically not educated and lack the graduate degrees needed to advance to higher levels of employment, or have a degree but remain unemployed but manage to put provide food for their families. Onu and Onu (2010) see low income earners as wage earners such as factory workers, semi-skilled and unskilled construction workers, workers from private sectors, and other junior or intermediate staff found in various government and private establishments. Ryder (1990) sees low income earners as those that are below the normal standard of living. They are poor and cannot meet their most important needs. According to NBS (2020), 40.1% of the total population of Nigeria was classified as poor. The monthly income of each individual in this category is less than N11, 500 per month. Low-income family in Nigeria is therefore a family

that earns the sum of N138, 000.00 per annum. In reality, those civil servants in low cadre, most employees who work outside the government sector or outside an organized private sector, as well as some self-employed Nigerians earn well below the national minimum wage of N30,000 per month which is equivalent of (N360,000) per annum. According to WHO, 2020, almost 83 million Nigerians live below the country's poverty line of N137, 430 per annum. By implication, many Nigerian families fall in this category. Low-income generally describes individuals and families that earn below the country's poverty line.

Coronavirus

Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) is an infectious disease that has spread virtually to every country of the world. This disease is defined as illness caused by a novel coronavirus called severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2; formerly called 2019-nCoV) (Cennimo, Bergman & Olsen, 2022). Most people infected with the virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment, while some will become seriously ill and require medical attention. It has been observed that older people and those with underlying medical conditions like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, chronic respiratory disease, or cancer are more likely to develop serious illness. However, anyone can get sick with COVID-19 and become seriously ill or die at any age (WHO, 2020). To prevent the spread of Covid-19, there was a global lockdown which was a unique phenomenon prompted by the desire to protect lives from the ravaging pandemic. Internally, there was halt on every social and economic activities and the government restricted people's movement and instructed confinement to homes. On the other hand, countries locked down national borders, restricting the movement of people and goods thus impeding the economic and human relations that had previously existed among countries (Onyeaka et al, 2021).

Lockdown

Haider et al (2020) define lockdown as "a set of measures aimed at reducing transmission of COVID-19 that are mandatory, applied indiscriminately to a general population and involve some restrictions on the established pattern of social and economic life". Lockdown measures have been imposed worldwide to contain the transmission of coronavirus. The imposition of lockdown in Nigeria affected mostly people on private or informal sector, those who deal on certain economic activities like street trading and vending, micro and small scale manufacturing, repair and service provision, home-based enterprises, informal employees of formal enterprises. The vast majority of people who engaged in these economic activities are daily-wage earners who either rely on income generated from going to work at a physical location on a daily basis/weekly basis, be it as an employee for someone, or as a micro/small entrepreneur (Obiakor, 2020). Most importantly majority of these people earn below poverty rate. According ILO (2018), over 80% of workers in Nigeria work in informal sector. There is no doubt that COVID-19 negatively affected the socio-economic livelihood of low-income families in Nigeria, of which majority of them belong to the informal sector of the economy.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in Nigeria, one of the countries in Sub-Saharan Africa, precisely Enugu and Ebonyi States where the livelihood of families has been adversely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. The study employed survey research design. As at the time of this study, Nigeria has recorded a total of 254,221 confirmed cases of coronavirus, 3,142 deaths and 230,549 recoveries (Worldmeter, February 19, 2022). The respondents comprised 42 respondents from 35 years and above (N = 42). These respondents were chosen through availability and purposive sampling method. Thus, the respondents comprised unskilled workers from private sectors and small scale private business owners. This because the study aims at interviewing unskilled workers and small scale private business owners who have specific characteristics or experiences to give an in-depth insight on the objectives of the study. Specifically, the reason for selecting these categories of respondents was because the researchers believed to ascertain from them the true picture of the effects of COVID-19 on the well-being of low income families. Furthermore, this category of people seems to be mostly hit during COVID-19 pandemic. This is because small scale private business owners were restricted to carry out any economic business or go to work due to government lockdown policy. Twenty One (21) respondents were purposively selected from Enugu and Ebonyi States respectively. There was proper gender representation of respondents. The researchers and research assistants were spread between the selected states during the period of the study, this aided easy collection of data.

Data Collection

A face to face oral interview was conducted with all the respondents. This was done between January 31st and March 5th, 2022. Interview guide was developed with what exist in literature and validated using pre-interview exercise which informed the observed corrections on the guide before field work. Specific themes were spelt out in the interview guide however; the researchers remained as flexible as possible during the interview process using probing techniques to guide the respondents in giving in-depth insights in answering the research questions. The interview was focused on the socio-economic effects of COVID-19 on low-income families and the policies of the government to mitigate the effects. The essence of the interview guide was to make sure that the probes were sequential. To ensure the quality of the data collected iteration process were employed. The interview was interactive which gave the researchers the opportunities to review and improve on each interview to indicate grey areas that can be explored and probed in the next interview and you keep building from each interview until you reach the point of saturation. Each interview with each respondent lasted between 30 minutes to 50 minutes. The responses of the respondents were recorded with an electronics device. The consents of the respondents were also obtained before engaging them on the interview. The interviews were held in Enugu and Ebonyi States in the Southern part of Nigeria. The choice of the areas was because there are many open markets where small scale business owners and unskilled workers transact on daily basis. To capture the general views of the respondents on the study, the questions that guided the interview were as follows: How would you assess the effects of COVID-19 on socio-economic wellbeing of low-income families in Enugu and Ebonyi states? How will you describe the public aware of any government policies to cushion the effects of COVID-19 on low-income families in Enugu and Ebonyi states? The study employed manual content analysis to generate themes that formed the locus for synthesizing the research findings to find areas of convergence and variation of

opinion while comparing the findings with what exist in literature. At the end of the interview, we found out that the responses of our respondents closely matched out data and other available information on the effects of COVID-19 on the socio-economic wellbeing of low-income families by media reports and scholarly articles.

Ethical Clearance and Analytical Strategy

We sought and obtained informed consent for each of our respondents before carrying out the interviews. Furthermore, the collected qualitative data were analyzed using the manual thematic method, where the responses were transcribed with some beguiling phrases retained in the original versions and contexts.

Findings/Results

Respondents' Socio-Demographic Characteristics

The findings showed that equal males (50%) and females (50%) participated in the study. Majority of the participants ($N = 30$, 71.5%) were between the ages of 35 -55 years while ($N = 12$, 28.5%) were from 56 years and above. The graduates of tertiary institutions were ($N = 5$, 12%) while the respondents ($N = 37$, 88%) were secondary school and primary school certificate holders. All the respondents were married.

Results

The narratives of the respondents displayed different view points on the socio-economic effects of covid-19 on low-income families in Enugu and Ebonyi States of Nigeria. Coming up from these narratives, the findings were divided into three sections. In the first section, we assessed the socio-economic effects OF COVID-19 on low-income families. Second, we also assessed the government policies to mitigate the effects and third, we try to suggest what the government should do to curb the socio-economic problem caused by COVID-19.

Assessing the effects of Covid-19 on socio-economic well-being of families in Nigeria

The COVID-19 pandemic has devastated every sector of the economy in Nigeria leading to untold hardship on families, unplanned job loss, food insecurity, high cost of living and drastic reduction on the income of families. This section tries to assess the effects of COVID-19 on socio-economic well being of low-income families in Nigeria. Respondents were of the view that as a result of COVID-19 pandemic which spread like wild fire that there was lockdown in the country that made life miserable for families, especially poor and vulnerable families. Evidences have given that the Covid-19 and the subsequent lockdown to cushion the effects negatively affected livelihood and spending patterns of families. In one respondent's words:

COVID-19 and the following lockdown in Nigeria have really treated us badly. Covid-19 has forced many families in Nigeria into financial hardship. *Anyi aga survive kwanu ihe nke a?* (Are we really going to survive this bad condition?). In my family now, we feed two times or sometimes, once in a day because we cannot afford the three normal square meals. We have now resorted to using charcoal in cooking because we cannot afford buying cooking gas or kerosene. We have withdrawn our children from lesson classes because of the financial difficulties we are facing in the family. Things have drastically changed in this country and it is going down every day. (A 45- year old company driver, Enugu).

Another respondent was of the view that Covid-19 and the aftermath has scattered the family structure and the society. He believed that since the pandemic was recorded in Nigeria, there was an appalling hardship and unprecedented hike in the prices of goods and services, and many low-income families are being dragged to the mud because of the hard moment. More still, because there was what seemed to be a miserable future for the young, the youth engage in all sorts of crime to get money to take care of themselves. In his words:

Covid-19 pandemic *emego anyi aru na Nigeria* (has done us more harm than good). The rate of crime in the country is now too much since after the lockdown. The youth are now reverting to crime in order to get money because there are no job opportunities and nothing moves in the country socially and economically. The worst part of it is that with our meager income, you cannot afford to buy something reasonable from the market. The prices of goods and services rise on daily bases. The future heads of our families and future leaders of tomorrow are now engaged in ritual killings, banditry, kidnapping, yahoo boys gang group, cyber crime and the latest, taking of *mkpuru miri* (crystal Methamphetamine) which send the youth to their early graves. May God have mercy on us. (a 50-year old gateman, Ebonyi).

One of the respondents was of the opinion that Covid-19 has affected businesses even till now because businesses are now moving in small pace since there is little money in circulation. She maintained that the livelihood of many poor families is in danger:

This pandemic affected my business negatively. For us who travel to different places to buy the goods we sell, we spend a lot of money on transportation fare. To travel from Enugu to Kogi State to buy yam and other food items we sell, one pays a lot in transportation. This affects the prices of goods we sell, and with this it is very difficult for me to maintain my customers. As it stands now, I have no savings and I cannot boast of providing for my family as I used to do before because of hike in the prices of goods. (a 43-year old business woman, Enugu).

It is very common in Nigeria that those who have family members abroad normally receive some stipends from them as their home support. Unfortunately, the lockdown affected this support system as another man during the interview session lamented that Covid-19 has disrupted the social support from family members living abroad:

The help that I receive from my son in one of the African countries has ceased or drastically reduced since the outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic. Every month, I was sure of getting some amount of money from him to support what I earn here in Nigeria for our family up-keep. For some time now, he is finding it difficult to send something for the family (a 60- year old driver, Enugu).

Another respondent said that since the outbreak of Covid-19 that the number of his debtors has dramatically increased and as a result of that, she cannot provide enough for her family:

Truly, I am not blaming anybody at all; my blame and sadness go to Covid-19 and the lockdown imposed by the government to cushion its effects. As we are discussing now, many people owe me huge amount of money and I do not know what to do. How do you collect your money from those that it is very clear to you have been laid off their work at the peak of covid-19? There is also very clear evidence that some were laid off without income, some were underpaid, while some had their companies closed down (a 35-year old female recharge card seller, Enugu).

Another report from one of the respondents stated that Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown increased the level of domestic stress and conflict in low-income families:

In as much as the lockdown during the peak of Covid-19 pandemic helped to bring families together to share quality time with one another, however, there were increase in domestic violence in some of the low-income families. Some women were beaten up by their husbands while many children received domestic violence either from their parents or siblings. Moreover, the level of parents' anxiety and anger in such families were much because they were always thinking of how to make both ends meet in such a horrible condition, especially families with no income (52 year female food seller, Ebonyi).

Another interviewee also reported that the poor health systems in Nigeria helped to increase the number of deaths during the peak of Covid-19:

Most of our government hospitals that were supposed to receive patients during the peak period of the pandemic were in dilapidated state and not well equipped. The doctors and nurses were also not well prepared to tackle the sickness. As a result of this, many families lost their beloved ones because even when you were sick and may need malarial drugs and drip to regain your health, no doctor will be available to take care of you since they have presumed that the person had coronavirus and that they themselves had nothing to protect themselves incase if it was actually the virus. The low-income families could not even find money to buy panadol or malaria drugs thereby losing their loved ones. (a 47-year old seamstress, Ebonyi).

Government polices to mitigate the effects of Covid-19 on families

This section assesses the efforts of the Nigerian government to mitigate the effects of Covid-19 on low-income families. It has been on paper that the Nigerian government has taken numerous health, social, and economic measures to cushion the impact of Covid-19 on the poor and vulnerable families. However, the common recurrent themes from the family heads interviewed showed that the government has not really done much to alleviate the problems posed by Covid-19 on low-income families. They said that the policy responses brought by the government were not commensurate with the degree of the problem they encounter in their families. According to Dixit, Ogundeji and Onwujekwe (2020), the House of Representatives passed the Emergency Economic Stimulus Bill 2020 on March 24 to provide support to businesses and individual citizens of Nigeria, and the proposed law aims to provide 50% tax rebates to businesses that are registered under the Companies and Allied Matters Act so they can use this saving to continue employing their current workers. They also promised making cash transfers of N20,000 to poor and vulnerable households registered in the National Social Register. Further still, the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs Disaster Management and Social Development equally announced that it will provide food rations to vulnerable households. Here are some of the responses of the interviewees during the sessions:

It was true that the federal and state governments announced that they will ensure the rights to food, shelter and other basic necessities for people and families losing their jobs or income during the Covid-19 pandemic, especially the poor and vulnerable families, to be frank with you, in our own area we did not see any government officials distributing foods or any other basic amenities to people. Let our government tell themselves the truth! Somebody was telling me the other day that in most of the oversea countries, that there government will just keep their citizens' food packages at their door steps which will even take a family through one week. They need not to struggle for food or palliatives. The way things are done here in Nigeria looks like scam. (a 37-year old receptionist, Ebonyi).

They said that the government was distributing food items to households but most of the communities did not get any. In my own community in Abakaliki, nothing was given to us. We were just hearing of what the government gave to people especially in the North. Even the cash transfer we have been hearing about, we never received any cash transfer in our accounts. Yet the government has been propagating that they gave money to vulnerable families in Nigeria. Just look at me and my family, dying of hunger. Let them tell us where they transferred the money to (a 58-year old farmer, Ebonyi).

Our politicians are so wicked. The End-Sars protest has just opened our eyes to the evils of our so called rulers. Didn't you see in social media where our politicians packed the food items given to them to share to the poor households? *tufiakwa aru na-eme kwa na Nigeria* (God forbid evil). In fact there was nothing like palliative for the low-income poor families in my own area. It was actually meant for the rich and party members. The palliatives were not given to us because we do not belong to their party. (a 63-year old vulcanizer, Enugu).

The lockdown as a result of Covid-19 pandemic affected me and my family very seriously to the extent that we had nothing in the house to take care of ourselves since we depend on daily wages. We drank soaked garri most of time, and sometimes, we went to bed without taking cooked food. I heard that the government was sharing palliatives to people but none was given to us. (a 49-year old food seller, Ebonyi).

Suggested solutions to the government to curb the socio-economic effects of Covid-19 pandemic on low-income families in Nigeria

This section explores opinions on what the government should do to curb the socio-economic effects of Covid-19 pandemic on low-income families in Nigeria now and in the future, bearing in mind that the already set out policies have many limitations. The respondents made a lot of important suggestions, some of which were: Some made mention of creating meaningful job opportunities to the youth either through government or private sectors. Some suggested that the economy should be diversified. The government should invest heavily on agricultural sector so as to minimize food crisis now and in the future. More so, the government should set out sincere and transparent monitoring group all over the country to make sure that monetary support and incentives have a wider spread to support the poor and people in vulnerable employment. The poorest of the poor could be reached through trade associations, town union and other unions. Some of the respondents blamed the unpreparedness of the government in the economic, education and health sectors to the negative effect of the virus on low-income families in Nigeria. They suggest that the government should support the health sector through adequate funding, incentives for health workers and health care subsidies for the most vulnerable in the society because it will be a guard against future occurrences of any kind of disease. Some also suggest that the government should reduce their spending on administration and governance so that enough money will be allocated to health and education. They also appeal to the government to give soft loans that will not attract much interest to the private business owners and traders. They equally suggest that an effective security system has to be set up, and this should accommodate every citizen of Nigeria. Some of the illustrative quotes include:

The government should know what to do to create jobs for our youths. The outbreak of covid-19 and the lockdown were eye opener to us here in Nigeria. It really showed us that our system is not working at all. Just because of few weeks lockdown, the rate of

crime has skyrocketed and many youth have now involved themselves into all sorts of crimes including cyber crime. Only that God saved me the other day, I would have lost the little amount of savings I have in the bank to the cyber scammers. Let the government provide jobs to our youths so that they can fix their intelligence and brain into something meaningful. They can as well sincerely offer loans to private sectors who will help to build up our economy. (a 36-year old female private primary school teacher, Enugu).

Hmmm! (exclamation!) In a country that majority earns below the poverty rate of \$2 per day that the legislatives live luxurious and exorbitant life. Please let the government cut down their administrative and governance funds and build up our health, education and economic sectors. We are gradually decaying in this country. We need efficient and effective health and hospital facilities in this country to contain Covid-19 pandemic, and also fight future diseases that may emerge. We need better educational structure and facilities to offer our children sound education as leaders of tomorrow. Our private sectors should be empowered to enable them create job opportunities to our young (a 40-year old private school driver, Enugu).

Let our government diversify our economy. Since we have seen that the period of oil boom has gone, let the government heavily invest on agriculture. I like to be optimistic. If the government can support the farmers in this country, food crises and poverty will find their way somewhere else. (a 58-year old farmer, Ebonyi).

Anytime the government want to share palliatives to people, if they want to be sincere, let them use town unions, organizations and associations in different localities in order to reach the target groups. An effective security system has to be set up in Nigeria whereby every citizen should be included (a 37-year old receptionist, Ebonyi).

Discussion

This paper was designed to find out the effects of Covid-19 on the socio-economic well-being of low-income families in Nigeria, to assess government policies to mitigate the effects and to proffer some practical solutions to the problem. The study was done in Enugu and Ebonyi States of Nigeria. The study found that the outbreak of Covid-19 and the lockdown imposed by the government to cushion the effects negatively affected the livelihood and spending patterns of families in Nigeria. It also found that the policies set out by the government to mitigate the effects were not beneficial to all especially the low-income families, the poor and the most vulnerable. The study also suggested some practical solutions to the government to curb the negative effects at present and in the future.

First, the study discovered that the Coronavirus Pandemic (Covid-19) has distorted aspects of human existence by suppressing business activities, social interactions, and employment opportunities. The Covid-19 pandemic and the after-effect negatively affected the social and economic progress of low-income families in Nigeria because it paralyzed the family system and their source of income. The hike in the prices of goods and services caused by Covid-19 lockdown made it very difficult for the low-income, poor and vulnerable families get their daily meals. Because of hardship caused by Covid-19, many families that usually get support from their family members could not do so because of bad economy. The lockdown restrictions from the government policies to curb the spread of the virus have interfered with the general well-being of families in Nigeria especially the low-income families, the poor and the vulnerable. There was increase in economic stress and domestic violence in families. Unemployment and the crises of Covid-19 led to high rate of crime in the society. Nowadays,

many youth are engaged in all sorts of crime and some are engaged in taking hard drugs in order to keep going. Findings from scholars from different parts of the world also showed that Covid-19 has devastating effects on socio-economic well-being of families. In a survey research by World Vision Albania (2020) on the impact of the outbreak of Covid-19 on wellbeing of children and families in Albania, it was found that the pandemic put strains on family finances, affected their employment and then made it difficult for them to meet their family needs. Also in research by UNICEF and UNDP (2020) on the impact of Covid-19 on households in capital territory of Philippines, they found that nearly all the respondents suffered severe financial consequences due to the crisis and it was assumed that the rate of poverty may increase. Miassi, Dossa and Akdemir studied the socio-economic impact of coronavirus (Covid-19) on households in Africa, Europe, Asia and Latin America and discovered that the pandemic has negative effects on the households of the continents studied.

Second, this study discovered that the policies set out by the government to mitigate the negative effects of the pandemic have largely been inadequate in performance because of so many deficiencies associated with them. The following strategies were used: the policy of economic stimulus bill 2020, conditional cash transfer to the poor and most vulnerable, Central Bank stimulus packages and food assistance (Babatunde & Olagunju, 2020). However, some of the policies were targeted towards formal sector businesses, ignoring the informal sector that produces about 65% of Nigeria total GDP and employs over 90% of the working population (Obiakor, 2020) Again, corruption and insincerity in the public sector have also contributed in limiting the effectiveness, of the food assistance and Cash transfers initiatives. Those who were assigned to distribute foods contributed by CA-Covid hoarded the food just for their own selfishness purposes. Also, the cash transfers of N20,000 to the poor and vulnerable households which was handled by the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development, through the National Social Register that had started long before the COVID lockdown was also criticized because of the inadequacies of the social register which contained only 2.6 million household out of over 87 million Nigerians living before the poverty line as at 2018 (Premium Times, October, 2020; Human Rights Watch, 2021). Although the government promised to increase this figure to 3.6 million household as a Covid-19 relief measure, yet not all the registered households received the cash transfer. This agrees with the study by Ibukun and Adebayo (2021) on the household food security and Covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria where they found out that there was gross inadequacy of government palliative support and distribution, and therefore recommends that policy implication, intervention and palliatives should be well planned and be consistent with household size and needs. Similarly in a study by Nwatu, Nwafor, Odo and Onalu (2021), they found out that the greatest challenge faced by many Nigerians amidst the pandemic is hunger and starvation and government palliatives were described as insufficient, resulting to high population of Nigeria still living below poverty line.

Lastly the study revealed some suggestions to the government on how to curb socio-economic effects of Covid-19 on low-income families. Employment should be created for the youth, both in the government and private sectors. Government should support the private sectors by granting them loans to boost their businesses and have a better chance of offering job opportunities to the youth. The government should diversify the economy and also invest heavily in agricultural sector so as to minimize food crisis now and in the future. The government should also set up sincere and transparent monitoring team that will see that any support from the government for the poor should be equitably shared and delivered accordingly. The government should also reduce their spending on administration and

governance and invest in agricultural, educational and health sectors. Furthermore, the government has to set up an effective security system in Nigeria. The federal government should draft and support legislation that recognizes Nigerians' right to social security, whereby entitlement for financial support for unemployed workers, those working in the informal sector and entitlement for children's benefits should be upheld.

Conclusion

The study assesses socio-economic effects of Covid-19 on low-income families in Enugu and Ebonyi States of Nigeria and the attendant lockdown policies by the government to stem the effect of the virus. The findings revealed that the government was not really prepared for the pandemic which has ravaged families economically and socially. The weak health system, absence of an updated social register, and inefficiencies in the coordination and distribution of support from Coalition Against Covid (CA-Covid) all contributed to lapses in cushioning the crises of Covid-19 pandemic on the socio-economic livelihood of low-income families. The government is encouraged to strengthen the social protection system in the country since majority of Nigerians are engaged in private sector of the economy, so many survive on daily income. With the imposition of lockdown which disrupted the economic activities, majority of Nigerian had no access to alternative sources of income or palliatives. The government is also advised to reinforce the agricultural, educational and health sectors of the country, as well as setting up an effective security system in the country.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicting interest to declare.

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